

Toward Society 5.0: A Conceptual Framework for Advancing Women’s Participation in ICT and Overcoming Systemic Barriers

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Abstract. The ICT industry continues to exhibit significant gender imbalance across operational, tactical, and strategic roles, with women remaining underrepresented. This disparity is a critical challenge, particularly as gender equality—central to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 5—is essential for sustainable development and emerging societal models such as Society 5.0. Addressing this imbalance is therefore vital to advancing SDG 5, especially Target 5b, which emphasises the use of ICT to empower women.

To support progress, a systematic literature review of thirty-eight studies was conducted to identify barriers to women’s participation in ICT and propose actionable solutions. Key barriers include individual-level factors such as imposter syndrome, low self-efficacy, and technophobia. These are often shaped by broader societal influences, including limited early exposure to technology, which can affect confidence and long-term participation.

Additional barriers exist at societal, educational, and organisational levels. The literature identifies effective interventions, including mentorship programmes, increased visibility of female role models, awareness initiatives, improved recruitment practices, and better access to career guidance and ICT-related information. These findings informed the development of a conceptual framework to help ICT organisations identify barriers and implement targeted strategies. Such interventions are essential for promoting gender equality and fostering a more inclusive and diverse ICT workforce.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Gender, Inclusivity, Underrepresentation, Women, Society 5.0, Sustainable Development Goals, Barriers.

1 Introduction

Women constitute approximately 56% of global undergraduate enrolments; however, they remain significantly underrepresented in Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM) and particularly in Information and Communication Technology

(ICT) [36]. This imbalance is a global concern and is especially pronounced in developing regions such as Africa, where ICT fields remain predominantly male-dominated. Evidence suggests that female exclusion begins early and intensifies over time [1], indicating that entrenched socio-cultural norms continue to limit women's progression despite formal equality measures.

This challenge is critical within the context of Society 5.0, a human-centred paradigm that integrates advanced digital technologies to address societal challenges and enhance quality of life [22]. Its success depends on inclusive participation and equitable access to digital skills. Women's underrepresentation in ICT therefore constrains innovation, limits talent diversity, and undermines social inclusivity.

The issue also contributes to labour shortages, skills gaps, and reduced workforce adaptability [20]. Gender equality is central to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 5, which seeks to empower women globally [34]. Research shows that empowering women enhances economic growth by expanding productive participation [8]. Persistent gender disparities further exacerbate shortages in critical skills such as coding and scientific expertise.

A systematic literature review (SLR) identified key barriers, including socio-economic constraints, gender bias, pay inequality, and limited access to quality education. These challenges are particularly acute in low-income contexts [9], with 69% of ICT employers citing tertiary subject choices as a major barrier to entry [29]. Barriers are commonly grouped into individual, family, societal, and labour-market factors [3].

This study extends this framework to align identified barriers with targeted solutions. Its objective is to propose integrated strategies that support inclusive digital transformation, contribute to SDG 5, and advance Society 5.0. Despite global commitments, progress remains slow, with estimates suggesting that full gender equality may take decades or longer [34].

Accordingly, this paper addresses the following research question: *What barriers hinder women's participation in the ICT sector, and how can a tailored conceptual framework help overcome these barriers in advancing toward Society 5.0?*

2 Literature Background

This study extends beyond identifying barriers to women's participation in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) by emphasising practical, actionable solutions. While gender inequality in ICT remains a global challenge, particularly in developing regions, addressing it requires evidence-based interventions that promote inclusion, skills development, and equitable career opportunities [36].

The study proposes a multi-level strategy aligning barriers with targeted solutions across individual, educational, societal, and organisational levels. At the individual level, interventions focus on improving confidence, self-efficacy, and digital skills. Psychological barriers such as imposter syndrome, technophobia, and low confidence often deter women from ICT careers [1]. Mentorship, early exposure to technology, and career guidance can foster sustained interest and competence.

At the educational level, improving access to quality STEM education and inclusive learning environments is critical. Partnerships between institutions and industry can provide practical exposure through internships and digital training [29]. Addressing subject selection is essential, as 69% of ICT employers identify it as a barrier to entry [29].

At the societal level, cultural norms and gender stereotypes continue to shape participation. Early exclusion from STEM education reinforces disparities [1]. Public awareness campaigns, community initiatives, and visible female role models can challenge these perceptions.

At the organisational level, companies should adopt inclusive recruitment, ensure pay equity, and implement flexible work arrangements. Leadership development and diversity strategies further support career progression and workforce diversity [20].

Aligning these strategies with global priorities, including Sustainable Development Goal 5 and Society 5.0, is essential. Promoting women's participation in ICT is critical for building inclusive, innovative, and sustainable digital economies.

3 Research Method

The research methodology employed in this paper is a systematic literature review (SLR) [19]. The data sources included: Wiley Online Library, Sage Journals, Springer and IEEE Xplore digital library.

The following search string was used across the selected data sources: *((Actions) AND (Empowerment) AND (Women) AND (ICT)), ((Factors) AND (Barriers) AND (Women) AND (ICT) AND (Underrepresentation)), ((Underrepresentation) AND (Women) AND (ICT) AND (Roles)), ((Underrepresentation) AND (Women) OR (Females) AND (Software industry) OR (Software development))*.

These search strings were designed to capture literature addressing the actions and factors influencing women's empowerment, the barriers contributing to their underrepresentation in ICT, and their participation in roles within the software industry and software development.

Inclusion criteria for this study were defined to ensure the relevance and quality of the selected literature. Only papers published between 2019 and 2024 were considered to capture recent developments in the field. All selected studies were required to be published in English. In addition, only papers from academic peer-reviewed journals or conference proceedings were included to ensure scholarly credibility. Finally, the studies had to be directly related to the topic under investigation.

3.1 PRISMA Flowchart

The PRISMA diagram in Figure 1 displays the process followed to acquire the research papers used within in the study. A total of two hundred and seventeen (217) records were identified using database searches and Google Scholar.

After an initial screening of the results, seventy-three (73) duplicate records were removed, leaving one hundred and forty-four (144) articles to be screened using the

predefined inclusion criteria. Following the application of the inclusion criteria, ninety-eight (98) records were excluded, resulting in forty-six (46) articles that were considered eligible for full assessment.

A detailed review of the remaining articles led to the exclusion of eight (8) studies, as their findings were not sufficiently relevant to the research question and did not focus specifically on technology when referring to STEM fields. Consequently, a total of thirty-eight (38) records were included in the final set of articles analysed as part of this systematic literature review (SLR).

Fig. 1: PRISMA Flowchart

4 Findings and Discussion

Thematic analysis was used to categorise the literature and identify key challenges women face in ICT and STEM, along with viable solutions. The findings are structured into themes, including identified issues (Section 4.1), proposed solutions (Section 4.2), and additional insights from the systematic literature review (SLR).

4.1 Identified Barriers to Women’s Participation in ICT

Women’s participation in the ICT sector remains limited due to several persistent barriers. Each of the identified barriers from the thematic analysis is discussed.

Hostile Work Environments and Organisational Cultures: A hostile work environment and exclusionary organisational culture remain major barriers to women’s participation in ICT. As noted in one study, “women are often not welcomed” [19]. Research shows that women frequently face challenging conditions due to the male-dominated nature of the sector [3, 5, 15, 21, 23, 24]. This “chilly climate” is characterised by exclusion, limited support, and restricted opportunities for advancement. Women may be excluded from high-impact projects that enable career progression and may also encounter sexual harassment and unwelcoming conditions, reinforcing the gender gap [3].

Gender bias and stereotypes further exacerbate these challenges. Bias arises from assumptions that women are less capable in ICT due to perceived deficiencies in logical and analytical skills [32]. However, ICT careers also require essential soft skills such as communication and teamwork. Studies consistently highlight the negative impact of stereotypes on perceptions of women in ICT [2, 3, 15, 23, 24, 26, 32]. For example,

[32] found that 74.6% and 75.6% of respondents agreed that stereotypes contribute to negative perceptions, often leading to women's contributions being undervalued.

These environments also weaken women's sense of belonging. Women frequently feel excluded rather than supported [19], and their efforts are often unrecognised, reducing motivation and increasing attrition [5].

Individual Level Barriers: Women in the ICT industry often face hostile work environments that create intrapersonal challenges, leading them to question their abilities rather than external conditions—commonly described as a “chilly climate.” Negative societal perceptions further reinforce the belief that STEM careers are unsuitable for women [2]. These challenges are intensified in male-dominated workplaces, where confidence may be undermined, resulting in reduced performance and underutilised potential [2].

Early exposure and leisure interests also shape career motivation, as activities like gaming are often associated with boys [9]. Women may therefore experience self-doubt if they lack such interests. Self-efficacy is critical for persistence and success in STEM [19], yet it may be weakened by workplace challenges and limited access to ICT resources, reducing engagement [21]. Lower confidence can decrease resilience and increase the likelihood of leaving the field.

Research shows a strong link between confidence, passion, and career persistence. Women who enjoy ICT careers are more likely to remain, while higher confidence supports advancement [19, 21]. Peer support further enhances participation [18], with online platforms such as Facebook and LinkedIn helping to reduce isolation and build networks [19].

Additional barriers include technophobia, which lowers confidence [30], and stereotypes that contribute to imposter syndrome [32]. Work–life balance challenges, particularly for mothers, also drive attrition [19], as many seek more flexible roles [31]. Flexible and hybrid work arrangements can improve retention and career progression [24].

Educational Barriers: [10] indicates that many women and girls leave high school with limited knowledge of STEM fields, resulting in missed opportunities for early exposure and career development. This lack of awareness contributes to women either not entering or leaving the ICT industry after graduation, as they often lack guidance on available career paths and workplace environments. In addition, many are unaware of the global impact of STEM careers and the inclusive cultures within some ICT organisations. Consequently, limited information reinforces perceptions of ICT as a male-dominated field, discouraging participation.

This knowledge gap can be addressed by expanding access to mentorship and professional networks that provide career guidance and information. According to [1], approximately 125 million girls of school age are not enrolled, and fewer than half progress to upper secondary education, where foundational STEM skills are developed.

Early exposure to STEM activities, such as coding and science experiments, can stimulate interest. Governments must improve access to education and uphold human rights, while communities and parents play a vital supportive role.

Furthermore, [32] highlights that inadequate career counselling limits awareness of diverse ICT roles, including emerging careers. In one study, 80% and 60% of participants in two groups did not pursue STEM due to insufficient information [32]. Similarly, [38] identifies limited industry knowledge as a key barrier. Sharing ICT career information through social media can broaden awareness and encourage participation.

Societal Barriers: According to [21], individuals are shaped by their social environments; thus, cultural beliefs, upbringing, and societal systems strongly influence how girls perceive career opportunities. This creates a disadvantage in many developing countries, where STEM fields are often viewed as more suitable for men. Consequently, girls may be raised to believe these careers are inappropriate for them. In many African contexts, cultural expectations also suggest that women pursuing professional careers may struggle to fulfil traditional roles as wives and mothers.

Research by [6] found that over 1,000 STEM graduates identified social stereotypes as a key factor contributing to women's low participation, highlighting the strong influence of societal perceptions. Similarly, [22] identifies societal norms and limited support for gender equality as major barriers to women entering and remaining in STEM careers.

These challenges are reinforced by practices such as child marriage, which restricts girls' access to education and widens gender disparities. Many girls must prioritise domestic responsibilities over schooling. According to [14], women's participation in formal employment remains low due to these obligations; in Uganda, 16% of girls marry by age fifteen and 53% by age eighteen [14]. Early marriage reduces access to higher education and limits ICT participation. Furthermore, [32] notes that many women marry before starting university.

Rigid gender norms undermine confidence [14], while limited access to technology and technophobia reduce interest in ICT [30]. Poverty and the digital divide further restrict access to digital skills [1].

Unfair Recruitment Practices: According to [10], employers in the ICT sector often demonstrate uncertainty when hiring female professionals, which contributes to gender bias during recruitment processes. This bias reflects doubts about women's professional competence in ICT roles. Such perceptions can negatively affect women's self-efficacy, ultimately encouraging them to leave the industry due to performance pressure or low expectations from colleagues. Common hiring biases relate to assumptions about motherhood, marriage, and women prioritising family responsibilities over careers [14]. These biases contribute to the low retention of women in ICT, further widening the gender gap [21].

Low retention is also linked to gender pay disparities, where 5–6% of women earn less than male colleagues in similar roles, particularly in fields such as Computer Science [25]. Since both genders perform similar tasks, compensation should be based on

skills and experience rather than gender [25], making pay inequality a form of gender discrimination.

To address these challenges, [18] suggests improving transparency in job descriptions, which may help reduce pay gaps and unfair remuneration practices. Government organisations often specify pay grades in job advertisements to promote equal compensation, whereas private organisations may lack such transparency, contributing to persistent inequality.

Lack of Support Structures: Findings show that 69.7% and 63.4% of two participant groups agreed that the absence of female role models is a barrier, as it limits their ability to find figures to inspire and motivate them in the ICT industry [32]. The lack of visible female role models reduces young girls' interest in ICT careers, as women in the industry have a limited pool of role models to identify with. According to [10], some women struggle to find role models relevant to their professional aspirations. Similarly, [3] indicates that the presence of female role models enhances self-efficacy and motivation among women studying STEM, thereby encouraging career entry.

The lack of female visibility contributes to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. According to [1], over one-quarter of females in the United Kingdom avoid technology careers because the sector is perceived as male-dominated, and only 22% of girls can name a well-known woman in technology. The statement “less participation causes less participation” [32] suggests that low female representation reinforces negative stereotypes about women's suitability for ICT careers, discouraging future participation.

Additionally, weak support networks further limit women's career sustainability, particularly given the workplace challenges they face [5]. Strengthening mentorship, networking platforms, and visibility of female ICT professionals can help address these challenges, as discussed in the role models and networking solutions section.

4.2 Addressing Identified Barriers to Women's Participation in ICT

As mentioned, women's participation in the ICT sector remains limited due to several persistent barriers. This section discusses possible remedies to address these barriers and enhance the participation of women in ICT.

Addressing Hostile Work Environments and Organisational Cultures, and Enhancing Hiring Practices through Law: A hostile or “chilly” workplace environment is a key factor driving women away from the ICT industry. Addressing this issue requires collaboration among stakeholders, including government bodies such as the Department of Labour, which enforces labour legislation. Policies aimed at eliminating discrimination are most effective when supported by formal regulatory frameworks.

Organisations can reduce hiring bias and gender disparities by ensuring transparent recruitment and promotion processes subject to external oversight, thereby limiting discrimination [4]. Promoting inclusive and diverse workplaces is also essential, as exposure to diverse colleagues fosters collaboration and mutual understanding [9].

Work–life balance challenges further influence women’s decisions to leave ICT careers, with many opting for flexible or reduced working arrangements. Supportive human resource policies—such as remote work, flexible schedules, and maternity leave—can help women remain in the workforce. Advances in digital technologies, including video conferencing, enhance the feasibility of such arrangements.

Training interview panels to recognise and mitigate gender bias is another important intervention [7], while hiring decisions should be based on merit rather than stereotypes [4]. Additionally, organisational initiatives such as diversity statements and programs like Video Interaction for Diversity in STEM (VIDS) promote inclusivity [7]. Appointing diversity officers and enforcing formal policies further support equality [25], alongside adherence to anti-discrimination legislation such as the Promotion of Equality and Prevention of Unfair Discrimination Act (2000) [30].

Career Guidance, Skills Development and Enhanced ICT Awareness: According to [20], the development of ICT programs has become an increasing government priority, highlighting the need for coordinated action between higher education institutions and external stakeholders to address limited awareness of STEM careers. Initiatives such as Girls’ Day target high school learners and women interested in STEM by introducing diverse scientific careers and challenging the perception of STEM as a “male domain” [4].

Higher education institutions can further support participation through academic advising, internships, and career and skills development programs that expand women’s exposure to STEM fields [5]. Organisations such as GirlCode also play a vital role. This women-led NGO offers coding courses at NQF Level 5, as well as bootcamps and hackathons designed for women aged eighteen and older [17]. Similarly, the African Girls Can Code Initiative (AGCCI), supported by UN Women, equips young women aged 17–25 with foundational ICT knowledge and coding skills through bootcamps and e-learning platforms [35].

Promoting diversity and visibility is equally important. Organisations can highlight women’s achievements in communications, while social media platforms enable experience-sharing through content such as “Day in the Life” videos. These initiatives foster belonging and encourage women to pursue and remain in ICT careers [7, 18].

Interventions Programs: Another way to increase women’s participation in ICT is through programs that promote STEM careers and empower them to pursue such paths. As discussed under career guidance, skills development, and access to information, initiatives like DO-IT Scholars and Grace Hopper Scholars provide targeted support [8]. DO-IT Scholars help students acquire technical skills and career competencies such as self-determination, fostering persistence in STEM careers, while Grace Hopper Scholars nurture interest in STEM regardless of financial background [8]. Additional programs, including W-STEM, Science for Girls and Boys, and Technovation Girls, aim to attract more girls into ICT fields. Social encouragement initiatives further enhance participation by improving self-efficacy and reinforcing that STEM careers are accessible to all genders [5].

Role Models and Networking Platforms: The findings of this systematic literature review (SLR) show that access to female role models and supportive networks significantly shapes women's perceptions of IT careers. Exposure to role models provides guidance and insight into workplace realities, while a lack of support networks remains a key barrier [5]. Professional platforms such as LinkedIn enable knowledge sharing and peer support.

Access to mentors positively influences career progression; however, mentoring is not always equally effective. Women from underrepresented groups, particularly women of colour, may struggle to form meaningful connections when mentors lack shared experiences [2].

Digital platforms offer solutions. The W-STEM app connects girls with role models, while platforms such as STEM and Medicine, Femmes de Science, and Girls Can Do I.T facilitate mentoring and provide career information [15].

Mentoring is essential for fostering interest and persistence in STEM [31]. Effective programs should equip mentors to address disparities, understand their roles, and promote positive attitudes among mentees [31].

5 A Conceptual Framework to Achieve the Representation of Women in ICT in Society 5.0

The primary aim of the conceptual framework presented in Fig. 2 is to address the barriers identified through the thematic analysis in Section 4.1 that may contribute to women leaving the ICT workforce, and to guide the implementation of targeted interventions (as discussed in Section 4.2) to address these challenges. In this way, efforts to reduce the underrepresentation of women in the ICT industry move beyond generic approaches to become more context-specific and effective. For example, in developing countries such as South Africa, where diverse societal cultures may influence organisational cultures, workplace practices, and hiring processes.

Organisations should begin by identifying the potential barriers that may exist within their contexts. They should then determine whether these barriers originate from within the organisation itself (internal factors, as indicated in Fig. 2) or from influences related to the individual employee or context (external factors, as indicated in Fig. 2). Once the root causes have been identified, necessary interventions can be implemented to address them effectively. Examples of interventions, identified in Section 4.2 are presented in Fig.2, as part of external and internal factors.

Furthermore, these interventions should be continuously monitored, evaluated, and reviewed, as illustrated in Fig. 2, to determine their effectiveness. Through ongoing assessment and refinement, organisations can ensure that the implemented actions contribute to reducing the attrition of women in ICT, thereby supporting the broader objectives of Society 5.0 and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

Fig. 2: A context-sensitive conceptual framework to achieve representation of women in ICT towards Society 5.0

6 Conclusion

This systematic literature review (SLR) addressed the question: What barriers hinder women’s participation in the ICT sector, and how can a tailored conceptual framework help overcome these barriers in advancing toward Society 5.0?

The findings provide an integrated view of factors contributing to women’s underrepresentation in ICT. Barriers to entry are largely driven by persistent stereotypes and gender biases that position ICT as a male-dominated field, discouraging early engagement among women. For those already in the sector, challenges are more career-related, including slow progression into senior roles and a lack of confidence from colleagues in their technical abilities, despite equivalent qualifications.

The review proposes a context-sensitive framework, suggesting that the gender gap can be reduced through targeted context-specific interventions. Key strategies include improved context-sensitive recruitment practices, stronger diversity and inclusion initiatives, and increased access to mentorship and role models. Importantly, women themselves can drive many of these initiatives by acting as mentors, role models, and advocates for STEM. Such efforts can challenge societal perceptions, inspire younger generations, and foster more inclusive work places to achieve the broader goals of Society 5.0 and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

However, the study has limitations. The proposed solutions were not empirically tested nor validated and remains largely theoretical. Additionally, the limited number of recent studies resulted in a relatively small sample, and the inclusion of only English-language publications may have introduced bias.

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